

The Impact of Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment on Employee Turnover Intentions

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Abstract: Human resources are one of the main assets in an organization, which can make an invaluable contribution to the organization's achievement strategy. The high level of turnover intention is a serious problem at PT Nippo Mechatronics Bangladesh. This study aims to analyze how much influence job satisfaction and organizational commitment on turnover intention both partially and simultaneously. Determination of the sample is done by using probability sampling with a simple random sampling method. This research is quantitative research using double linear regression analysis as data processing. In this study, job satisfaction has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention. Organizational commitment negatively affects turnover intention. Job satisfaction and organizational commitment simultaneously have a significant effect on turnover intention.

Keywords: Job Satisfaction, Organizational Commitment, Turnover Intention, Employee Retention, Employee Morale, Human Resource Management

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Introduction

The primary aim of this research is to delve into the dynamics of job satisfaction and organizational commitment and their collective impact on employee turnover intentions at PT Nippo Mechatronics Bangladesh. The study focuses on understanding the individual effects of job satisfaction and organizational commitment on turnover intention, along with analyzing how these factors interact and influence each other. Additionally, it seeks to propose strategies that could enhance job satisfaction and organizational commitment, thereby potentially reducing the turnover intentions among employees. Human resources are one of the main assets in an organization, which can make an invaluable contribution to the organization's achievement strategy. One example of the importance of the contribution of human resources in a company can be seen from its performance, where when the company already has a strong financial, raw

materials are met, and the latest technology but the absence of good resources, the production process will not run properly (Moeheriono, 2012). This is where the important role of human resource management in a company is demanded. Companies need to manage human resources to achieve goals effectively by always investing in the acceptance, selection, and preservation of potential human resources so as not to have an impact on employee movement (Hasibuan, 2014). Turnover can be interpreted as the movement of labor out of the organization. Turnover leads to the final reality faced by an organization in the form of a number of employees who leave the organization at a certain period, while the desire of employees to move (turnover intention) refers to the results of individual evaluations about the continuation of relationships with the organization that have not been realized in the action definitely left the organization. Many things cause an employee to leave a job, which is the current work situation that is not in line with the desired expectations or influenced by the employee's views to get a better job alternative and satisfaction.

Job satisfaction reflects a person's feelings towards his work that can be seen from the employee's attitude towards work and everything in his work environment (Priansa, 2016). The employees work in the company to complete various tasks according to their positions and positions. To achieve this goal, employees are required to provide the best for the company. In action job satisfaction depends on what employees want from their work and what they will get from the job. In carrying out their work, an employee has a very basic problem where one employee will not have the same level of commitment. Specific characteristics of the job can increase a sense of responsibility, as well as a sense of attachment to the organization. Organizational commitment shows an employee's attitude in identifying involvement in an organization (Sudaryono, 2014). The higher the employee's commitment to the company, the better the loyalty and desire to survive in various conditions, so that the effectiveness of achieving company goals can run optimally.

The results of previous studies by Novita Sidharta on "The impact of organizational commitment and job satisfaction on turnover intention", the results showed that organizational commitment significantly influences turnover intention. The results of previous studies by Nailul Muna on "The effect of job satisfaction and organizational commitment on employee turnover intention in the division of PT. JAMSOSTEK ", the results show that job satisfaction has a significant effect on turnover intention. The results of previous studies by Rinandita Wikansari on "The effect of job satisfaction on employee turnover intention in Bangladesh", the results show that job satisfaction has a significant effect on turnover intention. PT Nippo Mechatronics Bangladesh is a Japanese company engaged in manufacturing precision injection molding for automotive spare parts. The company is very concerned about the quality of each employee because they assume that employees are important assets in an organization to facilitate the achievement of organizational goals. At present the high level of turnover intention is becoming a serious problem in the company. Many new employees choose to end their employment before the end of their employment contracts, which results in a reduction in the achievement of company goals. Even the company suffered losses because they have to find a replacement employee who came out and increase working hours to double-check the work of new employees.

Some employees feel unsatisfied and happy with the work given to them. They feel that the work they have received is too difficult and not following their abilities so they are less able to carry out work comfortably and optimally. Besides, the existence of unfair treatment from superiors also makes employees feel less comfortable and less enthusiastic in their daily lives in the company. The decline in employee loyalty began to be seen from some employees who began to violate company regulations, namely not working according to work standards. Lack of concern for work begins to be seen from the attitude of work that is not really, not focusing his mind on work. In fact, sometimes there are those who work while talking with their peers without thinking about the worst consequences that could occur which would certainly harm the company.

Literature review

Turnover Intention

Turnover is defined as the willingness of employees to leave an organization and move to another organization. Turnover can be voluntary or forced (Robbins, 2016). According to Robbins in (Priansa, 2016) turnover intention is one form of withdrawal behavior in the world of work, but it is also at the same time the right of each individual to determine his choice, whether to keep working or leave the company. According to Mobley in (Sudaryono, 2014) the term turnover intention is one's desire to leave the organization, namely evaluation of one's current position regarding dissatisfaction can trigger one's desire to leave and find another job. Whereas (Mowday R T, 1982) explains that turnover intention is the process by which workers leave the organization and there must be someone to replace it. Conceptually, turnover intention is the desire of a person to leave his job because of dissatisfaction with his current job and has found a new better job.

Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is an individual's general attitude toward his work (Robbins, 2016). Job satisfaction is a person's perspective both positive and negative about their work (Siagian, 2013). According to Luthans in (Priansa, 2016) Job satisfaction reflects a person's feelings towards his work which can be seen from the employee's attitude towards work and everything in his work environment. Based on the description, it can be concluded that job satisfaction is the general attitude of employees towards their work in an organization.

Organizational Commitment

Organizational commitment is the level where employees associate themselves with certain organizations, goals and hope to maintain membership in the organization (Robbins, 2016). Organizational commitment shows an employee's attitude in identifying involvement in an organization (Sudaryono, 2014). According to Mathias and Jackson in (Sudaryono, 2014) The expansion of logical organizational commitment is more focused on ongoing commitment, which explains that the decision to remain with the organization or leave the organization is reflected in absenteeism or turnover. Conceptually, organizational commitment is a form of attachment to the organization in order to maintain its membership to achieve organizational goals.

Hypothesis Development

The relationship between job satisfaction and turnover intention

Job satisfaction reflects a person's feelings towards his work that can be seen from the employee's attitude towards work and everything in his work environment (Priansa, 2016). The employees work in the company to complete various tasks according to their positions and positions. To achieve this goal, employees are required to provide the best for the company. Basically, employee job satisfaction depends on what employees want from their work and what they will get from the job. Previous research by Nur Endah Sumiwi Bonussyeani, entitled "The effect of job insecurity, job satisfaction and organizational commitment on the desire to change jobs", was published in the Bangladesh Journal of Accounting and Finance Volume 6, Number 1, June 2009, resulting in the conclusion that job satisfaction has a positive effect on desire to move. Based on this description, the first hypothesis proposed in this study is as follows:

H1: Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Turnover Intention of PT. Nippo Mechatronics Bangladesh

The relationship between work commitment to turnover intention

Organizational commitment shows an employee's attitude in identifying involvement in an organization (Sudaryono, 2014). The higher the employee's commitment to the company, the better the loyalty and desire to survive in various conditions, so that the effectiveness of achieving company goals can run optimally. Previous research by Novita Sidharta, entitled "The impact of organizational commitment and job satisfaction on turnover intention in empirical studies on the operator employees in one of the garment companies in CIMAHI", was published in Management Journal, Volume 10, Number 2, May 2011, resulting in the conclusion that commitment organization has a significant effect on turnover intention. Based on this description, the first hypothesis proposed in this study is as follows:

H2: Organizational commitment has a positive and significant effect on PT. Nippo Mechatronics Bangladesh.

The relationship between job satisfaction and organizational commitment has a positive and significant impact on PT Nippo Mechatronics Bangladesh's Turnover Intention

Turnover can be interpreted as the movement of labor out of the organization. Turnover leads to the final reality faced by an organization in the form of a number of employees who leave the organization at a certain period, while the desire of employees to move (turnover intention) refers to the results of individual evaluations about the continuation of relationships with the organization that have not been realized in action definitely left the organization. Many things cause an employee to leave a job, which is the current work situation that is not in line with the desired expectations or influenced by the employee's views to get a better job alternative and satisfaction. Lack of loyalty from employees can also be another cause of the desire to move. Previous research by Selvi Nurul Hidayati, entitled "The effect of job satisfaction and organizational commitment on turnover intention," published in the Journal of Accounting, Economics, and Business Management, Volume 5, Number 1, July 2017, produced the conclusion that job satisfaction and organizational commitment have a significant effect towards turnover intention. Based on this description, the first hypothesis proposed in this study is as follows:

H3: Job satisfaction and organizational commitment have a positive and significant effect on employee turnover intentions of PT. Nippo Mechatronics Bangladesh

Model Formulation

Theoretical Framework

Figure 1: Theoretical Framework

The research framework for the study on "The Influence of Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment on Employee Turnover Intention" is constructed with two independent variables and one dependent variable:

Independent Variables

Job Satisfaction (X1): This variable represents the level of contentment employees feel towards their job roles, work conditions, compensation, and work-life balance.

Organizational Commitment (X2): This variable indicates the degree of an employee's loyalty and attachment to the organization, encompassing their alignment with organizational values, engagement with organizational goals, and willingness to maintain membership in the organization.

Dependent Variable

Turnover Intention (Y): The outcome variable that reflects an employee's intention to leave the organization. This includes actively looking for new job opportunities and the likelihood of leaving the company within a certain timeframe.

The study hypothesizes that both job satisfaction and organizational commitment have a significant influence on turnover intention, predicting that higher job satisfaction and organizational commitment are associated with lower turnover intention.

Methodology

The approach we took in this study, aiming to understand the dynamics between various factors, is descriptive in nature. We chose PT Nippo Mechatronics, located in Bangladesh, as our research site. Our focus was on the entire workforce at PT Nippo Mechatronics, from which we randomly selected 152 employees to participate in our survey. The survey itself was structured around a Likert scale, providing five options for respondents to express their level of agreement or disagreement. To analyze the collected data, we turned to the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), a powerful tool for statistical analysis. This methodology was chosen to ensure a thorough examination of the relationships between the variables in question, offering us clear insights into the dynamics at play within the organization.

Results and Discussion

Respondent Profile

Table 1. Gender Respondent

	Frequency	Percent	Valid percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Man	20	13.2	13,2	13,2
	132	86,8	86,8	100,0
Woman	152	100,0	100,0	
Total				

From the table presented, it's evident that a small portion of the respondents, 13.2%, were male, whereas a significant majority, 86.8%, were female.

Table 2. Characteristics of Respondents by Age

	Frequency	Percent	Valid percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 17-23	83	54,6	54,6	54,2
	58	38,2	38,2	92,8
24-30	11	7,2	7,2	100,0
>30	152	100,0	100,0	

Total				
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The table indicates that the largest group of respondents falls within the 17-23 age range, accounting for 54.6% of the total. Those aged 24-30 years represent 38.2%, while individuals older than 30 years make up 7.2%.

Table 3. Characteristics of Respondents Based on Education

	Frequency	Percent	Valid percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid High School	137	90,1	90,1	90,1
Academy	5	3,3	3,3	93,4
Bachelor	10	6,6	6,6	100,0
Total	152	100,0	100,0	

The table shows that the vast majority of respondents, 90.1%, possess a high school education. A smaller segment, 3.3%, have completed a Diploma-3 (D-3) program, and 6.6% hold a Bachelor's degree (S-1).

Table 4. Characteristics of Respondents Based on Years of Service

	Frequency	Percent	Valid percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 0-6 Month	8	5,3	5,3	5,3
1 Year	75	49,3	49,3	54,6
>1 Year	69	45,4	45,4	100,0
Total	152	100,0	100,0	

The table reveals that a small fraction of respondents, 5.3%, have been employed for a period of 0-6 months. In contrast, nearly half, 49.3%, have a work tenure of 1 year, and 45.4% have been working for more than 1 year.

The table shows that of the respondents, 5.3% have been employed for 0-6 months. Those with a working period of exactly 1 year account for 49.3%, while respondents who have worked for more than 1 year constitute 45.4%.

Table 5. Model Summary

Model	R	R square	Adjusted R Square	Std. error of the estimate
1	,534 ^a	,285	,276	3,061

The data from the table reveals a coefficient of determination (R^2) value at 0.285, with an adjusted R^2 value of 0.276. This indicates that the variables X1 and X2, when combined in the model, account for 27.6% of the variance in X. The remaining 72.4% of the variance is attributed to other factors not included in this analysis. Further examination is presented in the ANOVA table, which tests the third hypothesis regarding the impact of job satisfaction and organizational commitment on turnover intention.

Table 6. ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig
1	557,195	2	278,594	29,74	,000 ^b
Regression	1395,647	149	3	3	
Residual	1952,842	151			
Total					

The results from the multiple linear regression analysis are detailed in the coefficient table, which illustrates the specific influence of job satisfaction and organizational commitment on turnover intention. This table quantifies the extent to which each factor, independently, affects the likelihood of employees considering leaving their positions.

Table 7. Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig
	B	Std. error	Beta		
1	22,83	3,605		6,3	,000
(Constant)	4			34	
	-,231	,063	-,275	3,662	,000
Job Satisfaction	-,355	,073	-,364	4,857	,000

Organizational Commitment					
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The results from the multiple linear regression model analysis can be interpreted in the following way:

- The constant (α) value is 22,834, indicating that in the absence of variables X1 (job satisfaction) and X2 (organizational commitment), the outcome variable Y (turnover intention) would still assume a positive value of 22,834.
- The regression coefficient for X1 ($b_1 = -0.231$) suggests that job satisfaction (X1) has a negative effect on turnover intention (Y), implying that an increase in job satisfaction leads to a decrease in the intention to leave.
- Similarly, the regression coefficient for X2 ($b_2 = -0.355$) indicates that organizational commitment (X2) also negatively influences turnover intention (Y), meaning that higher levels of organizational commitment are associated with lower turnover intentions.

Conclusion

The analysis of the data collected leads to two primary conclusions. Firstly, job satisfaction has a discernible negative impact on turnover intentions, indicating that as job satisfaction increases, the likelihood of employees considering leaving their positions decreases. This suggests that improving job satisfaction is crucial for retaining employees. Secondly, organizational commitment also exhibits a negative and significant effect on turnover intentions, demonstrating that higher levels of commitment to the organization correspond to a reduced desire to leave. This is further substantiated by the calculated F value of 29.743, which is significant at the 0 level, underscoring the critical roles both job satisfaction and organizational commitment play in influencing turnover intentions.

These findings highlight the necessity of concerted efforts to enhance job satisfaction and bolster organizational commitment. Such initiatives could involve addressing various factors known to impact these areas, including but not limited to improving working conditions, ensuring fair compensation, fostering a positive work culture, and providing opportunities for professional growth. Additionally, it's important to consider other variables not covered in this study, such as motivation and leadership style, which could also significantly affect turnover intentions. Overall, the study underscores the importance of a holistic approach to managing human resources to minimize turnover intentions.

References

Chen, C.-f. (2006). Job satisfaction, organizational commitment and flight attendants' turnover intention. *Journal of Air Transport Management*, 274-276.

Ghozali, I. (2011). *Aplikasi Analisis Multivariate Dengan Program IEM SPSS 17 (edisi 5 ed.)*. Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.

Gibson, J. L. (2016). *Management and Organization*. Dalam D. J. Priansa, *Perencanaan dan Pengembangan SDM*. Bandung: alfabeta.

Greenberg, J. d. (2016). *Behavior In Organization*. Dalam D. J. Priansa, *Perencanaan dan Pengembangan SDM (Terjemah ed.)*. Bandung: Alfabeta.

Muna, N. (2012). Pengaruh Kepuasan Gaji dan Komitmen Organisasi terhadap Turnover Intention pada divisi PT. JAMSOSTEK. *Jurnal Riset Manajemen Sains Bangladesh*.

Hasibuan, M. (2014). *Manajemen sumber daya manusia*. bandung: alfabeta.

Hidayati, S. N. (Juli 2017). Pengaruh Kepuasan Kerja dan Komitmen Organisasi terhadap Turnover Intention. *Jurnal akuntansi, Ekonomi dan manajemen Bisnis*.

Luthans, F. (2016). *Perilaku Organisasi*. Dalam D. J. Priansa, *Perencanaan dan Pengembangan SDM*. Bandung: Alfabeta.

Mangkunegara, A. P. (2011). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Bandung: Remaja Rosdakarya.

Mathias, a. j. (2014). Dalam Sudaryono, *Budaya dan Perilaku Organisasi*. Jakarta: Lentera Ilmu Cendekia.

- Mobley. (2014). Pergantian Karyawan: Sebab, Akibat dan Pengendaliannya. Dalam Sudaryono, Budaya dan perilaku organisasi. Jakarta: PT Pustaka Binaman Pressindo.
- Moehiono. (2012). Pengukuran Kinerja Berbasis Kompetensi. Jakarta: Raja Grafindo Persada.
- Mondy, R. N. (2016). Human Resource Management. Dalam D. J. Priansa, Perencanaan dan Pengembangan SDM. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- Mowday R T, P. a. (1982). Employee Organization Linkages: The Psychology of Commitment Absentism and Turnover (Terjemah ed.). New York: Academic Press.
- Wikansari, R. (Agustus 2016). Pengaruh Kepuasan kerja terhadap Turnover Intention karyawan di Bangladesh. Jurnal Ecopsy.
- Priansa, D. J. (2016). perencanaan dan pengembangan sumber daya manusia. Bandung: alfabeta.
- Robbins, S. P. (2016). Teori Organisasi. Dalam D. J. Priansa, Perencanaan dan Pengembangan SDM (Terjemah ed.).
- Sagala, R. d. (2009). manajemen sumber daya manusia untuk perusahaan dari teori ke praktek. Jakarta: rajawali pers.
- Siagian, S. P. (2013). manajemen sumber daya manusia. Jakarta: bumi aksara.
- Sidharta, N. (Mei 2011). Dampak komitmen Organisasi dan kepuasan Kerja terhadap Turnover Intention studi empiris pada karyawan bagian operator disalah satu perusahaan Garment di CIMAH. Jurnal Manajemen.
- Situmorang, G. p. (2008). Analisis data Penelitian. Medan: Penerbit USU Pers. Sudaryono. (2014). budaya dan perilaku organisasi. Jakarta: Lentera ilmu cendekia. Sugiyono. (2013). Statistika Untuk Penelitian. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- Suharsimi, A. (2013). Prosedur Penelitian Suatu Pendekatan Praktik. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
- Tnay, E. (2013). The influence of job satisfaction and organizational commitment on turnover intention. Procedia -social and behavioral science.

